

Composite Hydrogels Based On Carboxymethylcellulose/Chitosan As Potential Adsorbent For The Removal Of Heavy Metal Ion Ce (IV) From Aqueous Solution: Performance, Kinetics, And Mechanism.

Renny J. Bastidas

Escuela de Ciencias Químicas e

Ingeniería

Yachay Tech

Urcuquí, Ecuador

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1420-8681>

Manuel Caetano Sousa

Escuela de Ciencias Químicas e

Ingeniería

Yachay Tech

Urcuquí, Ecuador

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8891-3140>

Lola De Lima

Escuela de Ciencias Químicas e

Ingeniería

Yachay Tech

Urcuquí, Ecuador

ldelima@yachaytech.edu.ec

Abstract—The aim of the present study is to synthesize (via chemical cross-linking) and characterize a hydrogel based on chitosan (CH), carboxymethylcellulose (CMC), citric acid (CA) and glycerol (GL) and determine its efficacy in the adsorption and removal of cerium (IV) ions from aqueous solutions. Different samples of hydrogels were synthesized with constant quantities of CH, CMC and GL, and varying concentrations of Citric Acid— 6 mL, 12 mL, 24 mL and 48 mL. The Attenuated Total Reflection – Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy verified its uniform structure and functional groups such as amines and esters which are considered excellent for the adsorption of heavy metals in aqueous media. The diffraction pattern seen indicated its amorphous character attributed to cross-linking. The morphology studies illustrated a heterogeneous porous distribution in the chains of the hydrogel structure with the presence of macropores. Spherical cavities were also seen. The degree of swelling was significant in the hydrogel with 6 mL at pH 7 assigned to its lesser chemical reticulation, in this case, citric acid being the chemical reticulant. Hydrogel sample with 3:1 volume ratio of CH:CMC:GL and 48 mL CA presented high adsorption capacity and its best kinetic fit was a mixed order model. EDTA was considered the best desorption agent in the study.

Keywords— *Hydrogel, Adsorption, aqueous solutions, Cerium, Reticulation, Composite.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The global environmental problem has different external causes, one of them is the accumulation of heavy metals [1]. Environmental pollution can be very harmful to people's health because human consumption and toxicity can lead to poisoning [2,3]. Moreover, water pollution has become a global issue due to incorrect usage and disposal [4]. Animals living in aqueous environments are also adversely affected [2,3]. As far as wastewater is concerned, pollutants are found and one of them are heavy metals. Therefore, it is essential to conserve existing freshwater reserves and improve wastewater treatment techniques. Adsorption is considered one of the most suitable for eliminating heavy metals in aqueous media and has been fundamental for the treatment of wastewater [3]; The metal subjected in this study is cerium. It is added to the environment through the medical and automobile industry [5]. This metal can seriously damage the lungs through direct ingestion or inhalation causing pulmonary embolism. Because of this, efforts have doubled to find treatments that can remove the cerium metal from the environment [5,6]. One of the treatments include

the use of hydrogels, which is economical, simple, and environment friendly. Hydrogels are formed by hydrophilic three-dimensional polymer networks capable of absorbing large amounts of biological fluids and water. This property is significantly helpful in adsorption and removal of pollutants [7]. Carboxymethylcellulose and chitosan are the main components of the developed hydrogel in this study. These substances are found in large proportions, specifically in Ecuador, even in the shrimp shells residue [8]. They have zwitterionic properties in which its anionic and cationic union provides a significant adsorbing character [9].

This work aimed to study the adsorption and removal of cerium from aqueous solutions using hydrogels based on chitosan, carboxymethylcellulose, citric acid, and glycerol. The functional groups were verified using Attenuated Total Reflectance-Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR). The physicochemical characterization of the hydrogel was determined through the use of X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) and X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS). Morphology was evaluated through Scanning Electron Microscopy. The adsorption mechanism and kinetics were also analyzed, as well as its desorption and swelling capacities.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Materials and Reagents

Reagents used for hydrogel synthesis were Chitosan food grade (Biofitness), anhydrous acetic acid for analysis, carboxymethyl cellulose sodium salt high viscosity, glycerol, anhydrous citric acid. For desorption studies, cerium ethylenediaminetetraacetic Acid (EDTA) and sulfuric acid were used.

B. Hydrogel Synthesis

The hydrogels used in this study was synthesized via cross-linking or solution polymerization. For the first procedure, chitosan (CH), carboxymethylcellulose (CMC), citric Acid (CA), and glycerol (GL) solutions were prepared. The reagents were weighed with an accuracy of 0.0001g in the analytical balance. 2 g of CH was dissolved in 100 mL 2% (v/v) acetic acid to make 2% (w/v) solution and formed a pH of 6. Then, 2 g CMC was dissolved in 100 mL distilled water to obtain a solution 2% CMC (w/v). 2 g CA and 10 mL GL were dissolved in 100 mL distilled water to obtain a

solution of 2% (w/v) and 10% (v/v), respectively. Stirring was kept during approximately 3 hours and was stopped as soon as the compounds had crossed the molecules and were completely homogeneous. The second procedure carried out was the preparation of composite hydrogels. Four hydrogel samples were made with constant quantities of CMC (24 mL), CH (8 mL), and GL (9 mL), but each hydrogel have varying concentration of citric acid, 6 mL for 6CA hydrogel sample, 12 mL for 12CA, 24 mL for 24CA and 48 mL for 48CA and were labeled accordingly. A commercial mixer was used to mix all solutions in approximately 10 to 12 minutes. The order of the solution mixture was as follows: CMC, CH, CA, GL. Hydrogels were drifting in centrifuge tubes to use an ultrasound bath for 40 minutes at 40 °C. After that, the stove was used to dry the hydrogel sample in 40 minutes at 80 °C. Hydrogel samples were then put in the freezer at -80 °C. Lastly, the samples were lyophilized using a lyophilizer with the condition of -45 °C and a pressure of 42 kPa. All hydrogel samples were then labeled and stored for its characterization and use for the adsorption and removal of cerium (IV) from aqueous solutions.

C. Hydrogel Characterization

1) *Attenuated Total Reflectance-Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR-FITR)*: The functional groups containing the hydrogel in its crossover chain was characterized using the FTIR spectroscopy using a Cary 630 with 1-Bounce Diamond ATR Accessory. The spectra were obtained in the range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} , and spectra resolution of 4 cm^{-1} and 32 scans.

2) *X-Ray Diffractometry (XRD)*: The crystalline structure of hydrogels was studied by X-Ray powder diffraction: A Mini-flex-600 from Rigaku, with a D/tex Ultra 2 detector. The X-Ray generator, Ni-filtered Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.15418 \text{ nm}$), was fixed at 40 kV, 15 mA. For collecting data, powder samples were placed on a glass sample holder, and the selected angular region was $2\theta = 5^\circ - 90^\circ$ with a step width of 0.01° .

3) *X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy*: Analysis was performed to get chemical information on some selected CMC/CH composites hydrogels. A PHI 5000 Probe III Scanning XPS Microprobe from Ulvac phi, inc. For the sample preparation, each sample was placed onto a polymeric-based adhesive tape that was hold in a metallic mesh. High resolution deconvolution was performed using Tougaard background subtractions, and Voigtian and Gaussian functions. The software used for this purpose was Fityk and Ominic [10].

4) *Morphology Images*: A morphology study of dried composites hydrogel was carried out using a SZX16 stereomicroscope at different magnifications (Olimpus) and nano tomography equipment which is a lab-based Bruker Sky Scan 2211b.

D. Swelling Studies

A dry hydrogel sample of approximately 15 mg with 10 mL of distilled water was put on three solutions with different pH concentrations: acid, medium and basic. Data collection was done: first at 5 min, second at 30 min and subsequently every hour. The data obtained was then used in a time vs. swelling graph. The percentage of swelling of each hydrogel was calculated using Eq. (1):

$$E_{sr}(\%) = \left(\frac{W_s - W_d}{W_d} \right) \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

E. Adsorption and Desorption Studies to evaluate Performance, Kinetics and Mechanism.

1) *Adsorption Evaluation using Ultraviolet-Visible (UV-Vis) Spectrophotometry*: UV-Vis spectrophotometer SPECORD S600 from Analytik Jena, with a polychromator with concave holographic grating and photodiode array (1024 pixels), with a wavelength range of 190-1100 $\text{nm} \pm 2 \text{ nm}$. The light sources used are a halogen lamp for the VIS and infrared region and a deuterium lamp for the UV region. The system is controlled by the modular software package WinASPECT. UV-Vis instrument was calibrated using standard Ce preparations from cerium sulfate (IV) in H_2SO_4 1 N.

2) *Adsorption Kinetics*: The hydrogel samples were subjected to adsorption testing, containing 10 mg per sample in a 50 mL aqueous solution, the liquid medium was composed of Cerium metal (100 ppm). In addition, a series of batch experiments were programmed, where 150, 160, 170, 180, 190 or 200 mg/L of Ce (IV) solution was added to individual 250 mL (beaker or volumetric flasks) containing 10 mg of 48CA hydrogel. All experiments were performed under ambient conditions and samples were gently shaken by hand during the measurement time, to establish adsorption equilibrium. Then, 3 mL of liquid phase of each solution obtained were added to a quartz cell, light absorbance of the samples was measured at 316 nm using spectrophotometer, and the results were used to calculate the amount of adsorption per used sorbents, at equilibrium.

3) *Desorption Studies*: Experiment desorption was done with EDTA and H_2SO_4 at different concentrations, in both cases at 1 M and 0.5 M. The desorption test was in batch mode ($T=24 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $t=72 \text{ h}$). 50 mL of EDTA and H_2SO_4 were used, with a weight of approximately 10 mg for each hydrogel composite. Five types of hydrogels were utilized and were submerged at 100 pm cerium. The percentage of desorption in each component was calculated using the Eq. (2)

$$D_e(\%) = (X_{ma} - X_{md}) \times 100 \quad (2)$$

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Hydrogel Characterization

1) *Attenuated Total Reflectance-Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR-FITR)*: The FTIR spectra of the different hydrogel composite samples were observed to be similar, exhibiting the characteristic bands of the chitosan and carboxymethylcellulose. The widest band can be seen in the range of 3000 – 3600 cm^{-1} , attributed to the N-H stretching vibrations of free amino groups and O-H stretching vibrations. The asymmetric stretching of the C-H bonds to the groups of $-\text{CH}_2$ to at 2934.7 cm^{-1} and the groups $-\text{CH}_3$ are at 2883.2 cm^{-1} . The bands between 1650 and 1610 cm^{-1} are linked C = O, known as stretching vibrations of amino acetylated groups (amide I) [11-12]. Vibration bending of the N-H and $-\text{NH}_2$ groups in chitosan is associated with the free amino groups in the band at 1591.6 cm^{-1} , as are the symmetrical stretching vibrations of the COO groups in the CMC. While in the 1500 cm^{-1} and, it is

associated with ionic interactions or hydrogen bonds between chitosan and CMC. In the 1442 cm^{-1} band, the vibrations of the NHCOCH_3 groups occur with a slight symmetrical bending of the methylene CH_2 group. In the bands 1395.2 cm^{-1} and 1321.5 cm^{-1} , asymmetric bending of the methyl group $-\text{CH}_3$ occurs. The stretching vibrations of the CN group (amide III) correspond to the 1315 cm^{-1} band, as does the N-H stretching of N-acetyl-glucosamine. C-N stretching vibrations in free amino groups appear at 1207.5 cm^{-1} . The asymmetric group C-O-C belongs to the B-glycosidic bond and exists in the 1103.9 cm^{-1} vibration band. The stretching vibration of the C-O bond (ring saccharide) are found consecutively in the bands of 921.9 , 1012.2 , 1029.4 cm^{-1} . The 786.8 cm^{-1} vibration band is related to the bending of the C-H group of the β -linked glycosidic bond [11,12]. The ester bond formation occurs in the 1730 cm^{-1} band. The presence of CMC and CA produces an esterification reaction. In addition, a different intensity was observed for each type of CA hydrogels, which is given by the degree of chemical reticulation [13-15]. With the data obtained from the FTIR enlargement region shown in Figure 1, it can be indicated that hydrogels synthesized have a uniform structure and functional groups such as amine, among others, which are excellent for the adsorption of heavy metals in aqueous media [15].

Fig. 1. FT-IR enlargement region $1850\text{-}1125\text{ cm}^{-1}$ of different hydrogel samples: a) Blue = 48 CA, b) Red = 24 CA, c) Green = 12 CA, d) Sky blue = 6 CA

2) *X-Ray Diffractometry*: The diffraction pattern of the hydrogels illustrated the crystalline peak width to $2\theta \approx 21.6^\circ$ suggesting that the hydrogels are highly amorphous, due to its cross-linking.

3) *X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy*: The peaks of the binding energy appearing at $284.3\text{-}284.93\text{ (eV)}$ is assigned to represent links $-\text{CC}-$ and $-\text{CH}-$; 286.415 (eV) represent links $-\text{CN}-$, $-\text{CO}-$, and $-\text{COH}-$; 287.809 (eV) represents links $-\text{C}=\text{O}$, $-\text{OCO}-$, $-\text{NC}=\text{O}$ and $-\text{CN}$; lastly, 288.95 (eV) represents links $\text{COO}-$ and $-\text{COOH}$ [11,12]. The signal associated with COOH and CO groups increments with higher concentrations of CA, which confirms the incorporation of CA into the hydrogel matrix. The high-resolution spectra N1s of hydrogel composite show two peaks at 400.00 eV and 401.775 eV associate to bonds $-\text{NH}_2$ and $-\text{O}-\text{C}-\text{N}$, and NH_3 respectively. The increment of the signal at 401.775 eV with CA concentration is due to the formation of ionic crosslinks between $-\text{NH}_2$ groups from CH and COOH groups from CA and CMC, by ion interactions, or hydrogen bonds [16].

Based on the different chemical characterizations carried out, chemical and physical cross-linking was confirmed. The groups formed were: amines, ester, hydrogen bond, ionic bond, alcohols, amides.

B. Morphology Studies

Fig. 2 shows images with the use of nano tomograph, heterogeneous porous distribution was observed in the chains of the hydrogel structure, with presence of macropores. No visible porous interconnectivity was seen. Roughness was also evident due to the presence of intermolecular hydrogen bonds between CMC and CH [15].

Fig. 2. Hydrogels ramifications of at different concentrations of citric acid seen in nano tomograph; left image – 48CA, right image – 6CA.

Fig. 3. Structure of the hydrogel at different magnifications. a) 1 mm, b) 2 mm, c) $200\text{ }\mu\text{m}$, d) $500\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ Photographs by stereomicroscope.

Spherical cavities were also observed in stereomicroscope, as shown in Fig. 3. It can represent surface action and agitation force, as its structure possesses chain formation and electrostatic interaction between polymer molecules. Sphere cavities can be filled with water or any liquid substance, increasing their weight. These cavities can return to their natural form after evaporation. It regenerates after drying completely [17].

C. Swelling studies

The degree of swelling of the hydrogels as a function of time was analyzed at different pH levels: (1) neutral, pH 7.0; (2) acid, pH 3 and (3) alkaline, pH 11. Disintegration was observed with 6CA hydrogels in acid medium, due to lack of hardness in reticular walls. On the other hand, 12CA, 24CA and 48CA hydrogels were suitable in acid media. In the alkaline medium, it was observed that all hydrogel samples

presented swelling, 6CA having the highest swelling ratio. Tremendous swelling was observed with 6CA at neutral media attributed to the junctions of the bonds that can be stretched. Therefore, the capacity of swelling increases when the chemical reticulation of the structure is less.

D. Adsorption studies

1) *Adsorption evaluation using UV-Vis Spectrophotometry:* Hydrogel samples of 6, 12, 24, and 48 in 100 Ce ppm were analyzed. The 6CA hydrogel sample disintegrated in the procedure resulting in incomplete adsorption analysis. Figure 4 shows the degree of adsorption of the other hydrogel samples over time. The data presented that the hydrogel sample 48CA showed excellent adsorption capacity, concluding it as a robust adsorber. Because of that reason, we focused on 48CA hydrogel sample in evaluating the kinetic studies.

Fig. 4. Adsorption capacity of the hydrogel samples at different citric acid concentrations: 12 CA, 24CA and 48CA.

Fig. 5. Adsorption kinetic parameters of 48CA hydrogel composite in 200 mg L⁻¹ aqueous solutions of Ce (IV).

2) *Adsorption Kinetics:* Fig. 5 illustrates the adsorption kinetic of 200 mg L⁻¹ aqueous Ce (IV) solutions onto 5 mg of 48 CA material. It was observed that Ce (IV) rapidly adsorbed onto 48 CA, and reached equilibrium after ~10 min. Residual Standard Errors (RSE) were calculated and compared, to evaluate the performance of the kinetic models and the residual graphs were plot and analyzed. After that, it revealed that the best fit was the mixed order model (MO). A summary of the kinetic parameters obtained for Ce (IV) concentrations of 150, 160, 170, 180, 190, and 200 ppm, using MO model is presented in Table 13.

TABLE I. SUMMARY OF THE KINETIC PARAMETERS OF DIFFERENT CE (IV) CONCENTRATIONS

Initial Concentration (mg L ⁻¹)	$q_{e, exp}$ (mg g ⁻¹)	$q_{e, fit}$ (mg g ⁻¹)	k_1 (min ⁻¹)	$k_2 \times 10^{-4}$ (min ⁻¹)	RSE (22 df)
150	~ 1352	1372 ± 10	0.16 ± 0.01	3.3 ± 0.1	9.98

Initial Concentration (mg L ⁻¹)	$q_{e, exp}$ (mg g ⁻¹)	$q_{e, fit}$ (mg g ⁻¹)	k_1 (min ⁻¹)	$k_2 \times 10^{-4}$ (min ⁻¹)	RSE (22 df)
160	~ 1490	1491 ± 10	0.09 ± 0.01	1.0 ± 0.1	7.72
170	~ 1523	1518 ± 07	0.09 ± 0.01	1.0 ± 0.1	5.11
180	~ 1600	1588 ± 11	0.03 ± 0.01	1.0 ± 0.1	6.05
190	~ 1595	1598 ± 10	0.03 ± 0.01	1.0 ± 0.1	5.92
200	~ 1597	1605 ± 10	0.025 ± 0.01	5.0 ± 0.1	3.25

Mixed order model (MO) is a hybrid kinetic equation, with a lineal combination of Pseudo first order (PFO) and Pseudo second order (PSO) models. PFO model can describe the initial stage of adsorption, when a few adsorbent active sites are occupied, while the PSO model represents the end stage of adsorption, when most of the active sites are occupied. The MO model, being a differential equation, was solved by using 4–5 order Runge-Kutta method. The values of the pseudo-first-order rate constant k_1 of the MO model range between 0.09 and 0.025 min⁻¹; and the values of the pseudo-second-order rate constant k_2 were between 1 to 5 × 10⁻⁴ g/(mg·min), respectively, implying that the adsorption is the combination of the pseudo-first- and -second-order kinetic processes. The overall process rate observed that the PFO rate (the rate of external diffusion) was in the same order of magnitude as PSO rate (the rate from adsorption at active sites), indicating that multiple rate limiting steps dominated the adsorption process. The highest values of the PFO and PSO rate were achieved at the beginning of the adsorption process and decreased quickly with time until equilibrium.

3) *Desorption Studies:* Hydrogel composite samples were treated with desorption agents, EDTA and H₂SO₄. The best desorption agent is EDTA 0.1 M, with a percentage of 78.5% for the 48 CA sample. While the worst sample is for H₂SO₄, 0.05 M the value of 16.2% for the 48 CA (NL) maybe because it did not receive lyophilized treatment. EDTA is a hexadentate chelating agent capable of forming a stable complex with heavy metal ions such as Ce (IV) [18].

IV. CONCLUSION

Increased adsorption capacity and chemical reticulation were attributed to the lyophilization treatment. Various features of the hydrogels (e.g., swelling, kinetics, etc.) were observed and was dependent on the citric acid concentration. Citric acid is an effective crosslinker promoting the formation of amide and ester bonds between CMC and CH compounds which are excellent for the adsorption of heavy metals in aqueous media. The hydrogels have heterogeneous porous distribution with the presence of macropores. The swelling capacity was tremendous at pH 7. The hydrogel-composite quickly absorbs Ce within 10 to 30 min; depending on the concentration of Ce (ppm). The hydrogel with the highest adsorption capacity was 48 mL CA lyophilized, so it was concluded that the more amides groups are formed, the adsorption will increase. The reduced swelling capacity of the hydrogels is promoting to carry further studies using similar substances as glycerol and citric acid and compare its character. Lyophilized compounds were much more effective than the non-lyophilized sample, so it is recommended to freeze the final product because it adds specific characteristics such as pore distribution, increased interconnectivity, among others.

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